

ISic2967

I.Sicily inscription 2967

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Iudica, inventory 2225

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI175462

1. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (αταχθονίοις) .
2. Καλποῦρνι
3. Σεκοῦνδε
4. χρηστὲ χαῖ-
5. ρε· ἔζησες ἔ-
6. τη ἰ'.
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645323

PHI 175462

Bibliography

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1959.0546

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.29

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